

1 **Il13ra1 functions in embryonic stem cell fate choice during endoderm lineage specification.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for Il13ra1 in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo*
11 *sapiens*.

12 Citations

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1. Osawa, M., Miyoshi, S., Copeland, N.G., Gilbert, D.J., Jenkins, N.A., Hiroyama, T., Motohashi, T., Nakamura, Y., Iwama, A. and Nakauchi, H., 2000. Characterization of the mouse interleukin-13 receptor α 1 gene. *Immunogenetics*, 51(11), pp.974-981.